

New Intermediates for Plastics and Coatings :

1. Preparation and Characterization of Methylene—Di-Salicylic-Acid*

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Polyfunctional acids such as phthalic anhydride, isophthalic anhydride, malic anhydride are used with poly-basic alcohols for condensation polymers, which are used in surface coatings. These polymers meet number of requirements of industry, but some improvements are still needed in surface coatings and can be achieved by using other polyfunctional acid. Methylene-di-salicylic acid (M.D.S.A.) is polyfunctional acid which can be used in place of above acids. Detailed experimental work has been carried out to prepare M.D.S.A. from salicylic acid and formaldehyde in presence of sulphuric acid as condensation catalyst. The conditions have been established to obtain optimum yield and quality of M.D.S.A. The process requires large quantities of sulphuric acid which could be reduced to greater extent by recycling this spent acid leading to the substantial reduction in the raw material cost. The physical and chemical properties of M.D.S.A. has been studied. The preliminary work with M.D.S.A. shows the great promise for its use as polyfunctional intermediate in condensation products suitable for plastics and surface coatings industry having specific end uses.

During the preparation of synthetic resins, and particularly the condensation polymers, large amount of work was done initially with the known polyfunctional acids and polybasic alcohols. It was however found that though these products gave quite satisfactory coatings, they still lacked in certain properties and it was felt that unless newer intermediates were developed, the coatings could not be improved further. It was from this point of view that the present work on M.D.S.A. was thought to be of interest.

The initial probe in the literature showed that salicylic acid could be converted into M.D.S.A. comparatively readily and as this is tetrafunctional material having two hydroxy and two carboxy groups, with the methylene bridge connecting two aromatic rings, it is quite possible that inclusion of such a material could result in products with specific properties.

Very little information is available on the use of M.D.S.A. also supported these views and the additional consideration for the taking of the project was that both the starting materials viz., salicylic acid and formaldehyde were locally available, work was therefore undertaken to standardize the method for preparation of M.D.S.A.

Methylene-di-salicylic acid was first prepared by Geigy¹ who obtained it by heating a mixture of salicylic acid and formaldehyde solution with hydrochloric acid. Later it was prepared by Kahl² and Madsen³ in practically the same way as Geigy. They used a much

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

larger amount of formaldehyde than theoretically required. Clemmensen and Heitman⁴ obtained a quantitative yield of M.D.S.A. by adding two moles of salicylic acid and one mole of formaldehyde to a 50% of aqueous solution of sulphuric acid and refluxing for 10 hrs. The weight of the 50% sulphuric acid was approximately six times the weight of salicylic acid in the charge. They reported that the product decomposed at 238° instead of melting. Smith, Sager and Siewers⁵ reported that they have prepared M.D.S.A. using 7 g. of trioxane, 100 ml. of glacial acetic acid and 1 ml. of concentrated sulphuric acid. In this reaction acetyl sulphate will form and may act as a catalyst for the reaction.

Apart from this, however no definite information is found in the literature regarding the optimum conditions of the preparations of M.D.S.A., the yield obtained, the properties of the compound and its technical applications. Investigations were therefore undertaken to prepare M.D.S.A. and confirm its properties and structure prior to study its usefulness in the various fields. The work is of particular importance in this country because of ready availability of commercial salicylic acid which needs outlets in addition to its use in pharmaceutical industry.

Preparation of Methylene-di-salicylic acid : Methylene-di-salicylic acid can be prepared by reacting salicylic acid and formaldehyde, using different condensation catalysts such as hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, sulphuric acid, phosphoric acid and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid. But in the initial investigation only sulphuric acid was used as condensation catalyst, because it was lowest in price and locally available material.

General Method : Salicylic acid and formaldehyde were taken in 250 ml. one neck quick-fit round bottomed flask. To this required quantity of sulphuric acid was added and refluxed, using water condenser for a known period of time. The product thus obtained was cooled, filtered under vacuum and washed several times with cold water and finally with hot water to remove traces of sulphuric acid and unreacted salicylic acid. It was then dried in vacuum oven at 110° for a period of 8 hr.

The properties like melting point, acid value, iodine value, molecular weight, specific gravity were determined by the standard methods.

Various reaction parameters such as quantity and percentage of sulphuric acid, duration of reaction and molar ratios of formaldehyde to salicylic acid were investigated. All the reactions were carried out at refluxing temperature.

Effect of reaction time : 27.6 g salicylic acid, 9.7 g of 30.90% formaldehyde and 180 g. of 50% sulphuric acid were taken in 250 ml one neck quick fit round bottomed flask and refluxed for different hours changing from 6 hr to 16 hr. The product obtained was cooled and filtered under vacuum and washed several times with cold water and finally with hot water to remove unreacted salicylic acid. It was then dried in vacuum oven at 110° for 8 hr. The results obtained are given in table 1.

Effect of molar ratio of formaldehyde : In this set of experiments, molar ratios of formaldehyde were changed from 0.8 mole to 1.5 mole. Remaining procedure was the same as mentioned in the previous experiments. The results obtained are given in table 2.

TABLE 3

Effect of sulphuric acid concentration on the yield of methylene-di-salicylic acid

Salicylic acid g.	Formaldehyde g.		Molar Ratio Salicylic Acid/Formaldehyde	Sulphuric acid		Reaction time hours	Practical yield g.	Theoretical yield g.	Percentage yield
	30.90%	100%		Percent	Quantity g.				
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	20	180	8	23	28.8	79.86
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	180	8	27	28.8	93.76
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	50	180	8	22	28.8	76.3
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	60	180	8	21	28.8	72.91
									(completely chars)
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	80	180	8	20	28.8	69.41
									(completely chars)

TABLE 4

Effect of proportion of sulphuric acid on the yield of methylene-di-salicylic acid

Salicylic acid g.	Formaldehyde g.		Molar Ratio Salicylic Acid/Formaldehyde	Sulphuric acid		Reaction time hours	Practical yield g.	Theoretical yield g.	Percentage yield
	30.90%	100%		Percent	Quantity g.				
27.7	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	100	8	23	28.8	79.86
27.7	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	120	8	24	28.8	83.33
27.7	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	140	8	25	28.8	86.80
27.7	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	180	8	27	28.8	93.76
27.7	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	40	200	8	23	28.8	79.86

TABLE 5

Properties of methylene-di-salicylic acid

Properties	Calculated	Observed
Melting point	238° (decom.)	238° (decom.)
Acid value	398.7 mg. koh/gm sample	397.2 mg. koh/gm sample
Iodine value	352.8	353.7
Specific gravity	1.43 at 24°	1.41 at 24°
Molecular weight	288.8	286.2
Elementary analysis	C — 62.4	C — 62.0
	H — 4.2	H — 4.9
	O — 33.4	O — 33.1

TABLE 6

Effect of recycling of sulphuric acid on the yield of methylene-di-salicylic acid

Salicylic acid g.	Formaldehyde g.		Molar Ratio Salicylic Acid/Formaldehyde	40% H ₂ SO ₄ g.	Reaction time hours	40% H ₂ SO ₄ recovered g.	Practical yield g.	Theoretical yield g.	Percen- tage yield
	30.90%	100%							
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	180	8	156	27	28.8	93.7
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	156+24*	8	156	27	28.8	93.7
27.6	12.62	3.9	2 : 1.3	156+24*	8	156	27	28.8	93.7

* 24 g. of Sulphuric acid was added to 156 g. of sulphuric acid (which was recovered from previous experiment) to make 180 g.

It was observed from the above experiments, that the maximum yield of M.D.S.A. was obtained when 27.6 g salicylic acid, 12.62 g of 30% formaldehyde, 180 g of 40% sulphuric acid were used and refluxed for 8 hr. Based on the results obtained from the detailed work done on preparation of M.D.S.A. a procedure was standardized for preparation of the product starting with 1 kg of salicylic acid and is given below :

1 kg salicylic acid, 460 g of 30.90% formaldehyde and 6.5 kg of 40% sulphuric acid were taken in a 10 lt round bottom flask fitted with water condenser and heated under reflux for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, and filtered using buchner funnel. The product was washed with cold water for several times and finally with hot water to remove sulphuric acid as also salicylic acid and dried at 110° for 8 hr under low vacuum. The yield obtained was 978 g corresponding to 93.5% of the theoretical yield.

Characterization of Methylene-di-salicylic acid : Methylene-di-salicylic acid was evaluated for some of its physical and chemical properties. It was found to be soluble in acetone, ether, alcohol, glacial acetic acid but insoluble in water, benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride etc. It gave the characteristic reactions of phenolic groups. It reacted with alcohols to give esters and it gave chelated coloured compounds with the ions of copper and iron.

In order to prepare pure crystallized M.D.S.A., the powdery material was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and tried to crystallize under the controlled conditions. The crystal shapes as observed under the microscope was, however not distinct. Repeated attempts were made to crystallize the compound under different conditions using different solvents like acetone, chloroform or solvent mixtures were unsuccessful, indicating that either there are interfering impurities in the compound or a mixture of different isomeric forms.

In view of this it was thought that a chromatographic separation could be attempted. This study indicated that the difficulty in crystallizing is not due to impurity which should have been separated by chromatographic method, the difficulties are likely to be of small quantities of other isomers. Naturally, these having same molecular weight it would not be possible to separate them by normal chromatographic method. Further study in this direction was not undertaken for simple reason that the major aim of preparation of M.D.S.A. was to study its suitability as intermediate for condensation products where these slight impurities or non-crystalline nature could not be of primary importance.

Infra-red spectrum of the purified material was taken to confirm the structure of M.D.S.A. and the various peaks indicated that the structure of M.D.S.A. is likely to be two salicylic acid units, joined by a methylene bridge in the ortho positions to the hydroxy groups. There is a possibility that methylene bridge might be in para position with respect to hydroxy groups. The infra-red spectra of the compound is given in Fig. 1. From the above data, the structure of M.D.S.A. has been suggested as follows :

Recycling of sulphuric acid : The results summarised in Table 4 show that, though comparatively satisfactory yields of M.D.S.A. could be obtained under optimum conditions, amount of sulphuric acid required is also sizeable and the process could not be really economic, if all sulphuric acid has to be thrown out. In view of this, need was felt to study the possibility of reutilization of sulphuric acid obtained in the mother liquor whereby only make up quantity of fresh acid needed.

27.6 g salicylic acid, 12.67 g 30.90% of formaldehyde and 180 g of 40% sulphuric acid were taken in 250 ml. one neck quick-fit round bottomed flask and refluxed for 8 hr, cooled and solid M.D.S.A. was separated and the remaining sulphuric acid was weighed. It was 156 g. The solid M.D.S.A. was washed with cold water and finally with hot water to remove unreacted salicylic acid. Dried and weighed the product. It was 27 g.

Fig. 1. Infra-red spectra of methylene-di-salicylic acid.

In the second experiment 27.6 g salicylic acid, 12.62 g of 30.90% formaldehyde and 156 g of sulphuric acid from above experiment and 24 g of 40% sulphuric acid was added to make a total quantity of 180 g. Water obtained in this reaction was negligible and will have very little effect on the percentage of sulphuric acid. Refluxed for 8 hr, cooled the solid was separated from sulphuric acid. In this experiment also 156 g of sulphuric acid was obtained. Washed the solid M.D.S.A. with cold and hot water. Dried and weighed, it was 27 g; similarly, third experiment was conducted and results are same as shown in the table 6.

The properties of M.D.S.A. obtained by recycling of sulphuric acid were determined. These are same as given in Table 5. Thus neither the yield nor the quality of the M.D.S.A. is affected by reutilization of sulphuric acid. This means that though initially large quantities of sulphuric acid is needed for cost calculation one can take only the make up quantity of acid.

As mentioned earlier, though theoretically different acid catalysts could be used, from the practical point of view there are certain limitations. Nitric acid being strong oxidizing agent has more side reaction than the required one, while the literature survey shows that hydrochloric acid is not suitable for this purpose. In view of this the only catalysts of interest other than sulphuric acid, are phosphoric acid and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid. Investigation therefore carried out where the effect of these catalysts and were studied. Though the product obtained was slightly better in colour, the facts that yield was not satisfactory, secondly properties like acid values were far from theoretical, it suggested that some side reactions are taking place and the reproducibility may not be of high order. Apart from this, cost of these catalysts are very high as compared to sulphuric acid and in view of no specific advantages, the catalysts do not appear to be suitable.

Conclusion : M.D.S.A. can be prepared readily by condensing commercial salicylic acid and formaldehyde in presence of sulphuric acid and yields over 93% can be obtained. Of the various catalysts studied, 40% sulphuric acid appears to be by far the best, both from the point of view of yield as also quality of the final product. The actual amount of sulphuric acid required per batch can be further reduced to a great extent by recycling the spent acid for limited number of cycles which leads to substantial reduction in raw material costs. The preliminary work with M.D.S.A. shows a great promise for its use as polyfunctional intermediate in condensation products suitable for plastics and surface coatings industries. The work in this direction is in progress.

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